

Analysis of Wake Characteristics for Contra-Rotating Propellers by CFD

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Abstract. This study aims to evaluate the wake flow characteristics of a Contra-Rotating Propeller (CRP) system through high-resolution numerical simulations and analyze their influence on propulsion performance. A CRP, consisting of two coaxial propellers rotating in opposite directions, enhances propulsion efficiency by recovering residual rotational energy and attenuating vortex intensity in the wake flow. This configuration contributes to fuel savings and greenhouse gas reduction, providing a practical solution for meeting environmental regulations such as the International Maritime Organization (IMO)'s net-zero target for 2050. In this study, the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) and Large Eddy Simulation (LES) models were applied to simulate the flow around a CRP system. Comparative analyses were conducted to examine differences in wake flow structures, thrust and torque characteristics, and tip vortex formation captured by each turbulence model. The vortex generation, development, and dissipation processes were visualized using Q-criterion and axial velocity fields, enabling a more detailed interpretation of the wake dynamics. The LES model, in particular, demonstrated superior capability in resolving fine-scale flow structures and capturing unsteady flow behavior, such as rotational energy recovery and vortex breakdown, which are difficult to predict with time-averaged models like RANS. All simulations were performed using STAR-CCM+ (version 18.06), and mesh convergence was validated using the Grid Convergence Index (GCI) method to ensure numerical reliability. The results confirm that LES is an effective tool for analyzing the complex hydrodynamic interactions inherent in CRP systems and provides valuable insights into wake flow physics. The findings of this study are expected to serve as a foundation for the design and optimization of CRP systems and contribute to the advancement of high-efficiency, eco-friendly ship propulsion technologies.

Keywords: *Contra-Rotating Propeller (CRP), RANS (Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes), LES (Large Eddy Simulation), Energy Efficiency, Turbulent Flow Analysis, CFD*

1 Introduction

1.1 Strengthening of IMO Environmental Regulations and the Need for Eco-Friendly Propulsion Systems

In response to the increasing demand for environmental sustainability, the International Maritime Organization (IMO) adopted the IMO 2023 Greenhouse Gas Strategy, which establishes an ambitious target of achieving net-zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from international shipping by 2050. Furthermore, during the 83rd session of the Marine Environment Protection Committee (MEPC) held in April 2025, the IMO introduced mandatory regulations requiring vessels of 5,000 gross tonnage and above to maintain their annual Greenhouse Gas Fuel Intensity (GFI) below a specified threshold [1].

GFI is a comprehensive metric that not only reflects the carbon characteristics of marine fuels but also incorporates the overall energy consumption associated with ship construction, propulsion efficiency, and operational conditions. Consequently, mere fuel substitution is inadequate to ensure compliance with the revised regulatory framework. Instead, technological innovations that enhance ship propulsion system efficiency have become imperative, thereby accelerating global interest in eco-friendly propulsion technologies.

Among such technologies, the contra-rotating propeller (CRP) system has emerged as a promising solution for improving propulsion efficiency. The CRP system employs two coaxial propellers rotating in opposite directions, wherein the aft propeller effectively recovers the rotational energy imparted by the forward propeller, reducing rotational losses and mitigating vortex strength [2]. This mechanism not only leads to substantial fuel savings but also contributes to the reduction of GHG emissions, positioning the CRP system as a viable and practical technology for compliance with emerging environmental standards.

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However, the inherent proximity of the two counter-rotating propellers inevitably results in complex vortex structures and pronounced blade-to-blade interactions within the wake field. Consequently, accurate performance predictions of CRP systems remain challenging when relying solely on conventional simplified models or experimental methods. Accordingly, the present study aims to quantitatively evaluate the improvements in propulsion efficiency afforded by CRP systems and assess their potential to comply with the latest IMO and MEPC environmental regulations.

1.2 Characteristics of Contra-Rotating Propellers (CRP)

The CRP system has been widely recognized as an effective solution for enhancing propulsion efficiency by recovering rotational energy losses and reducing vortex strength through the counter-rotation of the aft propeller, which cancels the residual swirl generated by the forward propeller. This mechanism contributes not only to fuel savings but also significantly reduces GHG emissions, thereby establishing the CRP system as a practical and viable technology for commercial ship applications.

Nevertheless, the inherently close configuration of the two oppositely rotating propellers induces complex wake vortex structures and significant hydrodynamic interactions, presenting substantial challenges in accurately predicting the performance of CRP systems. As such, conventional simplified models and experimental methods are insufficient for precise performance evaluation.

Moreover, the CRP system allows for the adjustment of various geometric and operational parameters, including blade number, diameter ratio, shaft spacing, and rotation speed ratio, all of which have a direct impact on propulsion efficiency and performance characteristics. Previous studies have reported that variations in these parameters can result in efficiency deviations of up to 5–10%, and even minor adjustments can lead to substantial changes in overall performance due to the strong hydrodynamic coupling between the two propellers [3].

Accordingly, a detailed analysis of the wake flow structures in CRP systems, capable of capturing subtle variations in efficiency, is essential for practical optimization and design refinement of CRP systems.

1.3 Necessity of CFD and Potential Flow Analysis

In this context, high-fidelity computational methods based on Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) have been actively employed to overcome the limitations of conventional approaches. While analyses utilizing the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations are effective for predicting overall flow structures, advanced turbulence modeling approaches such as Detached Eddy Simulation (DES) and Large Eddy Simulation (LES) have recently been adopted to capture detailed flow phenomena, including tip vortex dynamics, blade-to-blade interactions, and energy transfer mechanisms.

Several studies have highlighted the superiority of LES in resolving tip vortices and turbulent structures, making it an indispensable tool for quantitative analysis of the complex wake flows characteristic of CRP systems. LES incorporates wall treatment models such as the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy-Viscosity (WALE) model to accurately capture near-wall boundary layer flows, while directly resolving the energy cascade and vortex breakdown processes in the wake region, allowing LES to reproduce much finer flow structures than those attainable with RANS [4].

When applied to wake flow analysis, LES enables the quantitative evaluation of flow field characteristics using various diagnostic tools, including energy spectrum analysis, Q-criterion-based vortex visualization, time-averaged velocity fields, and turbulence intensity distributions, facilitating the identification of detailed turbulent structures that are difficult to resolve using RANS or potential flow methods.

Although previous studies have extensively investigated the general performance and flow field characteristics of CRP systems, the present study specifically focuses on the precise analysis of changes in wake flow structures resulting from variations in propeller rotational speed. In the case of electric propulsion vessels, which allow real-time adjustment of propeller RPM, such optimization is crucial for improving propulsion efficiency under varying operational conditions and is also highly relevant in terms of complying with environmental regulations.

Meanwhile, Paik et al. [5] conducted RANS-based simulations coupled with SPIV measurements to investigate the wake evolution and primary flow characteristics of CRP systems, while Paik [6] also employed RANS methods to analyze wake structures and performance variations. These studies demonstrated that while RANS methods are effective in evaluating the general flow characteristics, the inherent limitations of the average governing equations restrict their capability in resolving fine-scale vortex structures and turbulent flow phenomena, indicating the necessity for complementary high-resolution analysis.

However, due to the high computational cost associated with LES, its application across all rotational speed conditions is impractical. Therefore, this study adopts a complementary approach combining RANS-based simulations and potential flow methods. High-fidelity wake flow analyses are conducted using LES at selected

optimized rotation speeds and propeller configurations, while broader parametric studies are performed using potential flow codes and RANS simulations to identify optimal operating conditions.

Higher-order Boundary Element Method (BEM) approaches, such as the one developed by Paik, Suh, and Chun [7], have been widely applied for the performance evaluation of marine propellers under steady flow conditions. Although such methods have proven effective in general performance prediction, they remain limited in resolving the intricate wake vortex interactions present in CRP systems.

Accordingly, this study employs multiple turbulence models, including RANS, DES, and LES, to conduct a detailed investigation of the wake flow characteristics of CRP systems and to quantitatively analyze variations in flow structures and propulsion performance induced by changes in rotational speed. The commercial CFD solver STAR-CCM+ was utilized for all simulations, and the reliability of the results was ensured through grid convergence verification using the Grid Convergence Index (GCI) [8].

It is anticipated that the outcomes of this study will provide valuable insights for the optimization of CRP designs through the quantitative analysis of complex wake flows, thereby contributing to the development of eco-friendly, high-efficiency ship propulsion systems.

2 Methodology

2.1 Numerical Methods

In this study, a combined approach employing both Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and potential flow methods was adopted to accurately predict the wake flow characteristics of a contra-rotating propeller (CRP) system under varying rotational speeds. This complementary strategy enabled the leveraging of the strengths of each method while compensating for their respective limitations.

The CFD analyses were carried out using the commercial software STAR-CCM+ (Version 18.06), applying two turbulence modeling approaches as described in the following sections.

2.1.1 Numerical Methods : Potential

For the initial performance prediction and wake flow analysis of the CRP system, a potential flow code developed by Paik et al. [7] was utilized. This method is based on the Vortex Lattice Method (VLM), which assumes inviscid and incompressible flow conditions, and solves the Laplace equation, given as Equation (1), as its governing equation:

$$\nabla^2 \phi = 0 \quad (1)$$

where ϕ is the velocity potential. Source distributions and vortex lattices were placed on the blade surfaces to model the entire flow field. The source distribution was adjusted to satisfy the Kutta condition at the blade trailing edge, ensuring smooth flow separation and enabling physically consistent modeling of the wake vortex strength.

Additionally, to incorporate the interactions characteristic of CRP systems into the potential flow model, the flow field generated by the forward propeller was accounted for in the calculation of the aft propeller, thereby enabling the simulation of blade-to-blade interaction phenomena inherent to contra-rotating systems. Under this configuration, the aft propeller received the velocity field generated by the forward propeller as its inflow boundary condition, allowing the calculation of thrust, torque, and efficiency while considering the interference effects between the two propellers.

2.1.2 Numerical Methods : RANS

The Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) model predicts the mean flow field by applying statistical averaging to the governing equations through Reynolds decomposition, wherein the turbulent fluctuation components are represented as averaged terms. While the RANS model exhibits limitations in capturing complex flow phenomena such as boundary layer separation and large-scale vortex structures, it offers the advantages of high computational efficiency and the capability to predict the overall flow field characteristics.

The governing equations for incompressible Newtonian fluids are expressed using Einstein's index notation, as shown in Equation (2):

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + u_j \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_j} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial x_j^2} \quad (2)$$

where u_i is the flow velocity, ρ is the fluid density, p is the pressure, and ν is the kinematic viscosity. By applying Reynolds decomposition to the velocity components and performing time-averaging, the governing equations can be reformulated as the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations, given as Equation (3):

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j^2} - \frac{\partial \overline{u'_i u'_j}}{\partial x_j} \quad (3)$$

In these equations, the last term on the right-hand side represents the Reynolds stress tensor, which must be modeled using an appropriate turbulence model. In the present study, the Shear Stress Transport (SST) $k - \omega$ model was employed for propeller flow analysis. The SST $k - \omega$ model combines the strengths of the standard SST $k - \omega$ formulation in the near wall region with the SST $k - \varepsilon$ model characteristics in the free stream region, enabling more accurate predictions of flow separation and vortex generation compared to conventional two-equation models.

Although the RANS approach significantly enhances computational efficiency by averaging the entire flow field, its capability to resolve fine-scale vortices and turbulent structures is inherently limited by the turbulence model applied.

2.1.3 Numerical Methods : LES

Large Eddy Simulation (LES) applies spatial filtering to the Navier-Stokes equations, enabling the direct resolution of large-scale turbulent eddies through numerical methods, while the effects of smaller subgrid-scale (SGS) eddies are modeled using appropriate subgrid-scale models. The governing equations for LES are the filtered Navier-Stokes equations, given as Equation (4):

$$\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial t} + \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j^2} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j} \quad (4)$$

where τ_{ij} denotes the subgrid-scale (SGS) stress tensor, representing the effects of unresolved smaller eddies on the resolved flow field.

In the present study, the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy-Viscosity (WALE) model was employed to compute the turbulent viscosity, providing accurate predictions even within near-wall boundary layers. The WALE model adjusts the turbulent viscosity locally not only in regions of high shear stress but also in areas dominated by strong rotational vortices, offering superior accuracy in wall-bounded flow regions compared to conventional LES wall treatment models. This capability enables the high-resolution simulation of boundary layer separation as well as the generation and dissipation of tip vortices, even in highly complex flow regions.

By integrating CFD and potential flow analyses, a complementary approach was adopted in this study, wherein the potential flow method facilitated rapid parametric studies, while LES was applied for high-fidelity flow field analysis. This combined approach enabled comprehensive investigations of wake flow structures under various propeller rotational speed conditions, thereby supporting efficient and reliable performance assessments of the CRP system.

2.1.4 Nondimensionalization for Single Propeller and CRP System

For the analysis of the CRP system conducted in this study, the performance coefficients were nondimensionalized based on the forward propeller, following the methodology proposed by Van Manen [9].

The key nondimensional performance parameters advance coefficient (J), thrust coefficient (K_T), and torque coefficient (K_Q) are defined by Equations (5) – (7), respectively:

$$\text{Advance Coefficient}(J) = \frac{V_a}{n_f D_f} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Thrust Coefficient}(K_T) = \frac{T_f + T_a}{\rho n_f^2 D_f^4} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Torque Coefficient}(K_Q) = \frac{n_f Q_f + n_a Q_a}{\rho n_f^3 D_f^5} \quad (7)$$

where V_a is the inflow velocity, n_f and n_a are the rotational speeds of the forward and aft propellers, respectively, D_f is the diameter of the forward propeller, and T_f , T_a , Q_f , and Q_a represent the thrust and torque of the forward and aft propellers, respectively.

All nondimensionalization was performed using the rotational speed and diameter of the forward propeller as the reference parameters. This approach was adopted to evaluate the overall propulsion performance of the CRP system based on the forward propeller characteristics.

2.2 Target Model

For this study, a contra-rotating propeller (CRP) system developed by Hyundai Heavy Industries was selected as the reference model [10]. This CRP system was specifically designed for full-scale ship applications with the objective of maximizing propulsion efficiency and enhancing rotational energy recovery performance. The principal particulars of the analyzed CRP system are detailed in Table 1. Experimental fluid dynamics (EFD) data for this CRP system were obtained from model tests conducted at a scale ratio of 1/42.063 in the deep-water towing tank of the Hyundai Maritime Research Institute (HMRI). These tests, including open-water and self-propulsion experiments, have been reported in Min et al. [10] and provide the reference for the present CFD validation.

Table 1. Principal particulars of the contra-rotating propeller system analyzed in this study

	Forward Propeller	After Propeller
Diameter	9.1 m	7.9 m
Number of Blades	5	4
RPM	70.1 RPM	93.5 RPM
Thrust Ratio	50	50
Separation Distance	2.06 m	
Inflow velocity	12.86 m/s	

2.3 Computational Setup

All CFD simulations were performed using the commercial software STAR-CCM+ (Version 18.06). For the RANS simulations, the Shear Stress Transport $SST\ k - \omega$ turbulence model was employed to resolve the time-averaged flow field with particular emphasis on the accurate prediction of near wall boundary layer behavior. Throughout the entire blade surface, the dimensionless wall distance Y^+ was maintained below 1.5, as shown in Figure 1. For the LES simulations, the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy Viscosity (WALE) model was adopted to explicitly resolve the major turbulent structures. The time step size for both RANS and LES simulations was determined in accordance with the International Towing Tank Conference (ITTC) recommended guidelines [11] to ensure numerical stability and result accuracy. The computational domain was discretized using an unstructured mesh approach. Additional mesh refinement was applied in the vicinity of the propeller blades and within the downstream wake region to adequately capture wake contraction phenomena, turbulent energy transfer, and the formation and decay of tip vortices.

Figure 1. Computational mesh topology around the CRP propeller and downstream wake region used for CFD analysis.

2.4 Grid Convergence Index

To ensure the reliability of the CFD results, grid convergence verification was performed following the procedures recommended by the International Towing Tank Conference (ITTC). The Grid Convergence Index (GCI) method, as proposed by Celik et al. [8], was employed to quantitatively assess discretization uncertainty.

For this purpose, three levels of mesh resolution were prepared, and the sensitivity of the key performance parameters specifically, the thrust coefficient (K_T) and torque coefficient (K_Q) was evaluated. The GCI method provides an estimate of the discretization error associated with the finest mesh and enables the calculation of the convergence ratio (R_G), thereby facilitating the assessment of the grid independence of the numerical solution.

In this study, the GCI analysis was conducted for the LES simulations, and the coarse mesh configuration obtained from the analysis was subsequently applied in the RANS simulations. The results of the grid convergence studies for the thrust and torque coefficients are summarized in Tables 2 and 3, respectively.

Table 2. Grid convergence study of thrust coefficient (K_T) using Grid Convergence Index (GCI) method

	Num. of Grid [M]	K_T	R_G	GCI
Coarse	64.2	0.7498		
Medium	90.8	0.7571	0.102	0.137 %
Fine	128.4	0.7578		

Table 3. Grid convergence study of torque coefficient (K_Q) using Grid Convergence Index (GCI) method

	Num. of Grid [M]	K_Q	R_G	GCI
Coarse	64.2	0.1463		
Medium	90.8	0.1478	0.133	0.185 %
Fine	128.4	0.1481		

Figure 2. Grid convergence trend of thrust coefficient (K_T) and torque coefficient (K_Q) with respect to the number of grids.

As shown in Figure 2, the GCI values for both the thrust coefficient K_T and torque coefficient K_Q were confirmed to be within approximately 0.1%, thereby verifying the grid convergence of the numerical simulations. Figure 3 shows the computational domain and boundary conditions used in this study. A cylindrical domain was arranged along the propeller axis, with an axial length of approximately 8D, so that the inflow and the generation and dissipation of the wake could be adequately reproduced. The inflow was set as an inlet, where a uniform inflow velocity and turbulence conditions were imposed, while the outflow plane was defined as an outlet with a pressure-based boundary condition. The outer wall of the domain was assigned a slip boundary condition. This condition assumes that the fluid slides along the wall without friction, modeling a state without viscous resistance, in which the tangential velocity component is allowed to flow freely while the normal velocity component is suppressed. Through this setting, the growth of viscous boundary layers and shear stresses near the wall are eliminated, ensuring that the outer boundary of the domain does not impose artificial effects on the flow. Figure 4 presents the actual mesh distribution around the propeller blades and the wake region. From the front view and the axial cross-

section, boundary-layer resolving prism layers are arranged near the blade surfaces, with a gradual transition in grid size. To accurately capture the generation, development, and trajectory of the tip vortices shed from the blade tips, local mesh refinement was applied along the predicted vortex path. This finely refined region was designed to ensure that the vortices formed in the wake are stably resolved without numerical dissipation or artificial attenuation, and the mesh was extended downstream to encompass the entire wake dissipation region.

Figure 3. Computational domain and boundary conditions for propeller CFD analysis

Figure 4. Computational mesh topology around the propeller blade and wake region

3 Results and Discussion

In this study, the wake flow characteristics of a contra-rotating propeller (CRP) system were investigated through comparative simulations employing both RANS and LES approaches. These methods were used to calculate the axial velocity distribution and analyze the wake flow structures of the CRP system. In addition, the LES model was applied to compare the flow characteristics between the single forward propeller and the CRP configuration, with the objective of quantitatively demonstrating the efficiency benefits of the CRP system.

3.1 Comparison of Single Propeller Performance: EFD, CFD, and Potential Flow Analysis

3.1.1 Comparison of Single Propeller Performance Results

Figure 5. Comparison of single forward propeller performance results from EFD, RANS and potential flow analysis.

The performance results of the single propeller obtained from experimental fluid dynamics (EFD) tests conducted by Hyundai Heavy Industries were compared with those derived from CFD simulations and potential flow calculations. As shown in Figure 4, all three methods yielded closely aligned results and trends, with discrepancies within approximately 5%. This close agreement among the EFD, CFD, and potential flow results confirms the reliability of the numerical methods employed in this study.

3.1.2 Comparison of CRP System Propulsion Performance (POW) Results

Figure 6. Comparison of CRP system propulsion performance (POW) results from EFD, CFD (RANS, LES), and potential flow analysis

As shown in Figure 6, when compared with the EFD results, the numerical analyses conducted using potential flow, RANS, and LES exhibited only minor discrepancies in the absolute values of thrust coefficient (K_T) torque coefficient (K_Q), and efficiency (η_o). However, the differences remained approximately 5%, and the overall agreement across the entire range of advance ratios was very good. Furthermore, the general trends obtained from each numerical approach were almost identical to those of the experimental results. These findings indicate that the numerical methods employed in this study provide reliable results, thereby ensuring sufficient validation for subsequent analyses of the wake flow field and vortex structure characteristics.

3.2 Comparison of CRP Wake Flow Structures: RANS and LES

The wake flow structures of the CRP system were analyzed and compared based on simulations conducted using both RANS and LES approaches. In all cases, the flow fields were visualized using the nondimensional axial velocity component (u/U) as the reference parameter.

Figure 7. Comparison of CRP wake flow structures from RANS and LES analysis, visualized by axial velocity u/U contours

As shown in Figure 7, the comparison of CRP wake flow structures visualized by axial velocity (u/U) contours reveals distinct differences between the RANS and LES simulations. Figure 7(a) presents the results from the RANS simulation, where the wake flow exhibited a smoother and relatively simplified vortex structure as it progressed downstream. In contrast, Figure 7(b), which shows the LES simulation results, revealed more pronounced turbulent energy dispersion and finer vortex structures, representing a flow field that more closely resembles actual flow behavior.

These observations indicate that the higher spatial and temporal resolution inherent to the LES approach enables the accurate capture of fine scale vortices within the wake, thereby allowing for a more detailed and realistic analysis of the wake flow structures.

3.3 Comparison of Propeller Flow and Wake Structures Using LES: Single Propeller vs. CRP System

Based on the LES simulations, the wake flow structures of the single propeller and the contra-rotating propeller (CRP) system were compared and analyzed.

Figure 8. LES-based comparison of wake flow structures between single propeller and CRP system, visualized by axial velocity u/U contours

As shown in Figure 8, the wake flow structures of the single propeller and the CRP system, visualized by axial velocity (u/U) contours, exhibit distinct differences. Figures 8(a) and 8(b) present the LES based wake flow structures of the single propeller and the CRP system, respectively. As observed in Figure 8(a), the overall u/U values in the wake of the single propeller were relatively lower, indicating reduced thrust generation under the same inflow conditions. This result demonstrates that the CRP system, utilizing two counter-rotating propellers, exhibits more favorable wake flow characteristics and higher propulsion efficiency compared to the single propeller configuration.

3.4 Comparison of CRP Tip Vortex and Blade Surface Vortex Structures: RANS and LES

The tip vortex structures, and blade surface vortices generated by the CRP propeller were compared based on the results from the RANS and LES simulations, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Visualization of tip vortex and blade surface vortex structures of CRP from RANS and LES analysis using Q-criterion

Figure 10. Comparison of axial mean velocity distributions along downstream planes (spacing 0.5D) from RANS and LES analysis

The axial mean velocity distributions obtained from the RANS and LES simulations were compared. For both cases, planes were generated at uniform intervals of 0.5D along the axial direction to visualize the velocity distributions, as shown in Figure 10. Figure 10(a) illustrates the axial mean velocity distribution from the RANS simulation, while Figure 10(b) shows the corresponding results from the LES simulation.

Figure 11. Comparison of axial mean velocity distributions between RANS and LES results along the x-direction for CRP system

Figure 9(a) presents the wake field obtained from the RANS simulation. Since RANS is based on temporally averaged governing equations with turbulence treated through modeling, the vortices generated at the blade tips appear in the downstream region not as distinct linear structures but rather as diffuse, large-scale vortical patches. In particular, the vortex cores lose circulation rapidly due to excessive viscous diffusion and modeled turbulent viscosity, causing their radii to expand unrealistically and preventing the continuous helical structure from being maintained, leading to premature breakdown. This tendency becomes even more pronounced when the tip vortices from the forward (FWD) propeller are ingested by the aft (AFT) propeller blades. In this process, the phase-dependent stretching and dispersion of vortices are effectively eliminated by time-averaging, and the interaction is represented instead as artificially smooth and averaged behavior, deviating from the actual unsteady dynamics.

In contrast, Figure 9(b) shows the LES results, in which the dominant unsteady turbulent motions are directly resolved while only the smallest scales are modeled. The LES wake reveals continuous and coherent helical vortex cores originating from the blade tips that persist over a long downstream distance before undergoing staged breakdown into smaller-scale eddies. This behavior is clearly observed in the Q-criterion slices, which capture the coherent filaments in detail. As the tip vortices shed from the forward propeller are ingested by the aft propeller, their strength is either amplified or attenuated depending on the phase, accompanied by localized axial acceleration around the low-pressure cores, and eventually transferred into turbulent energy. Consequently, LES reproduces the entire vortex cycle from generation, convection through the propeller region, interaction with the aft propeller, to staged breakdown in a manner consistent with the actual physical flow.

These differences are also evident in the axial velocity distributions shown in Figure 11, where LES predicts approximately 4% higher downstream axial velocities compared to RANS. This is attributed to the ability of LES to preserve coherent vortex structures and maintain the swirl and axial momentum deficit within the wake, whereas

RANS excessively averages these effects and fails to sustain the outward propagation of vortices. Considering these physical characteristics, the choice of modeling approach becomes crucial in the case of a contra-rotating propeller (CRP) system, where the tip vortices shed from the forward propeller directly interact with the aft propeller. Such interactions influence not only the accuracy of wake predictions but also key propulsion-related aspects such as mixing losses, unsteady loading, cavitation inception, and tonal as well as broadband noise generated at blade-passing frequencies.

3.5 LES Based Comparison of Tip Vortex and Blade Surface Vortex Structures: Single Propeller vs. CRP System

A comparison of the tip vortex structures between the single propeller and the CRP system was conducted based on LES simulations, as illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12. LES-based comparison of tip vortex structures between single propeller and CRP system using Q-criterion visualization

Figure 12(a) shows the tip vortex structures generated by the single propeller, where strong tip vortices produced at the blade tips were observed to persist continuously downstream, maintaining their coherence over a long distance. In contrast, Figure 12(b), which presents the CRP system, reveals that the tip vortices generated by the forward propeller exhibited distortion and rapid dissipation due to their interaction with the aft propeller. This phenomenon can be attributed to the contra-rotating configuration of the CRP system, where the rotational flows from the forward and aft propellers interact and partially cancel each other, resulting in the dispersion of strong vortices into finer structures.

These observations confirm that, while the single propeller generates strong tip vortices that remain in the downstream wake, the CRP system effectively mitigates rotational energy losses by canceling the rotational components, thereby transforming large-scale vortices into finer and less intense vortical structures.

4 Conclusions

In this study, the wake flow structures, and propulsion performance characteristics of a contra-rotating propeller (CRP) system were numerically investigated, focusing on the effects of variations in rotational speed and the interaction between the forward and aft propellers. A combination of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and potential flow methods was employed to establish a comprehensive analytical framework, and the reliability of the numerical results was validated through comparisons with experimental data and grid convergence studies.

In the analysis of single propeller performance, the forward propeller demonstrated good agreement among the EFD, RANS, and potential flow results. However, noticeable discrepancies were observed for the aft propeller, particularly between the EFD and numerical analyses. These differences are likely attributable to uncertainties in the experimental setup and the operating conditions of the aft propeller, indicating the need for further investigation to accurately identify the root causes.

Regarding the overall performance of the CRP system, the LES simulations provided results that were more consistent with the actual propulsion performance compared to the RANS and potential flow analyses. Moreover, LES successfully captured the nonlinear flow characteristics associated with the interaction between the forward and aft propellers and quantitatively demonstrated the improvement in propulsion efficiency of the CRP system by accurately simulating the recovery of residual rotational energy from the forward propeller by the aft propeller.

The analysis of wake flow structures revealed that the CRP system significantly reduced axial wake losses and promoted earlier dissipation of tip vortices compared to the single propeller system. These findings confirm that the CRP system enhances propulsion efficiency and contributes to reductions in fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions relative to conventional single propeller configurations.

Overall, this study confirmed that the integration of various analytical methods enables a detailed and reliable analysis of the wake flow characteristics and propulsion performance of CRP systems. In particular, the LES approach proved to be a powerful modeling tool capable of capturing the complex interactions between the forward and aft propellers and elucidating turbulent energy transfer mechanisms.

Future research will focus on identifying the optimal rotation ratio under various rotational speeds and load conditions. Additionally, further investigations will address the effects of free surface interactions and evaluate in-service propulsion efficiency, supporting the practical application of CRP systems and contributing to the advancement of eco-friendly ship propulsion technologies.

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